

Comparative Study of Literacy Program Implementation on Tidore Island, North Maluku

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ABSTRACT : *This comparative study aims to analyze and compare the implementation of the School Literacy Movement (GLS) in SMA Negeri 1 and SMA Negeri 3 TidoreKepulauan City from 2016 to 2019. Observations and in-depth interviews were conducted at schools and libraries to collect data. The results showed that the implementation of GLS in SMA Negeri 1 was more effective than SMA Negeri 3, which only reached the habituation stage. The implementation of GLS in SMA Negeri 1 has reached three stages, namely habituation, development and learning, although some activities in the development and learning stages have not run optimally. So the efforts that must be made by schools and the government are conducting training for teachers, optimizing collaboration between schools and parties outside the school, encouraging innovation and creativity of teachers and students in implementing GLS.*

KEYWORDS -*Comparison, School Literacy, SMA, Tidore*

I. INTRODUCTION

The condition of literacy in Indonesia is still quite bad. According to the UNESCO Institute for Statistics report (2019), the reading ability level in Indonesia in 2018 only reached 57.3%, lower than the ASEAN average of 65.2%. In addition, a World Bank report states that only around 32% of Indonesian children have completed secondary education, far below the ASEAN average of 53%. This shows that there are still many people in Indonesia who lack literacy skills.

In 2018, BPS showed that reading interest in Indonesia was still quite low. According to the BPS report, in 2018 only around 21.8% of Indonesians expressed interest in reading. Meanwhile in 2017, this percentage was only 20.9%. This report also shows that interest in reading is especially declining among teenagers and young adults. This condition illustrates that there are still many people in Indonesia who lack interest in reading.

To increase students' interest in reading, the Government implemented the School Literacy Movement (GLS) which started in 2015. However, implementing this program policy is as easy as imagined, because according to Pradana, Fatimah, and Rochana (2017) in their study they explained that the obstacles to implementing the GLS program are: Teachers and students do not yet have sustainable awareness of implementing reading culture activities in schools through GLS. Not only that, the socialization carried out by the government regarding the implementation of GLS did not go well. Meanwhile, according to Huda (2017), nationally there are several obstacles encountered in literacy activities in schools, namely the unavailability of reading materials in schools, especially in remote areas, teachers' understanding of methods to increase students' reading interest in schools, and the lack of availability of reading corners to support school literacy program.

Meanwhile, Asmawan (2018) in his study found that the implementation of GLS faced various obstacles such as student incompetence, lack of books in the library, less strategic location, minimal facilities and the skills of library staff.

Seeing the obstacles in implementing the GLS program above, it is necessary first to understand the concept of literacy. Suyono (2011) explains that students can achieve effective and productive learning with a literacy approach so that it can help them in processing various information in the 21st century era. Musthafa (2014) states that efforts to create an intelligent and competitive society must be supported by literacy which is practiced through the ability to read, write and think critically.

Initially, the meaning of literacy in Indonesia was the ability of "literacy". However, over time, literacy develops into reading and writing skills. This expertise is basically directed at increasing broader literacy, which includes multiliteracy (Directorate General of PDM, Ministry of Education but Research and Technology, 2016). Meanwhile, the definition of literacy in Law Number 3 of 2017 concerning Bookkeeping Systems is interpreted as "the ability to interpret information critically so that everyone can access science and technology as an effort to improve the quality of their life". So literacy can be interpreted at the level of literacy activities in schools as students' understanding which falls into the category of important skills in understanding information. To improve students' character, ongoing activities are needed at school to shape students as lifelong learners.

Understanding school literacy within the scope of the GLS program is a strategy to help educational institutions become a place for sustainable learning, where citizens obtain, know and utilize information for writing, reading, communicating and interacting. This program also involves public participation (Directorate General of PDM, Kemendikbutristek, 2016). The GLS Program aims to build literacy activities in schools, encourage literacy in the school environment to be stronger, make schools a fun place to learn, and encourage school residents to manage knowledge and ensure that learning is sustainable by providing various reading collections and providing variety. type of reading model. (Directorate General of PDM, Kemendikbutristek, 2016).

While the stages of implementing the GLS program start from the habituation stage, the GLS program must be implemented in stages. First, students must be socialized about the importance of literacy. After that, the development stage begins with developing appropriate reading strategies. Finally, the learning stage begins by applying the reading strategies that have been developed. Apart from that, the GLS program, as stated in Minister of Education and Culture Regulation No. 23 of 2015, aims to shape students' character. The presence of this program in schools also encourages students' reading ability and competence to understand developments in science. The reading material presented consists of personalities, local, national and international cultural riches which are allocated according to the student's educational level (Faradina, 2017).

Relevant research on the GLS program has been widely studied in Indonesia. Especially related to the implementation of the GLS program. Not only that, several studies also explain the positive impact of these activities on students' reading ability. Research from Ramdhani, Rofi'uddin, and Santoso (2021) examined the comparative implementation of reading and writing culture in referral and non-referral educational institutions. The results of this study illustrate that facilities and infrastructure must support the diversity of reading materials borrowed by students, the diversity of literacy events in schools, literacy groups in educational institutions, and aspects of reading ability which are influencing factors. Then Khoeriyah, Indah, and Syam, (2021) also researched the implementation of GLS with a focus on the effectiveness of implementation and obstacles in Reading Challenge activities. The results of this research illustrate that the implementation of GLS has not been followed by all students. Then the obstacles in implementing the Reading Challenge program at SMA Plus Al-Ghifari show that students experience difficulties in describing it using a fishbone diagram because of the large number of school subject assignments. Meanwhile, Asmawan (2018) reviewed the role of school principals as leaders in educational institutions in facing obstacles to implementing GLS, namely that the curriculum developed must cover the development and application of science and technology and its influence on the community environment. To achieve this goal, it requires the work of all elements in educational institutions to increase the collection of reading materials, encourage a balance of learning inside and outside the classroom, and hold storytelling events, integrative learning pedagogical approaches, the addition of competent library staff, school literacy movements, and on an ongoing basis.

Furthermore, Joko's (2019) study found that the government's efforts to convey literacy program information were not evenly distributed to the community, especially in educational institutions and especially

teachers in schools, so that the effectiveness of conveying the objectives of the literacy program to teachers was not optimal. Meanwhile, the implementation of GLS also provides benefits for students' reading interest. Research results from Wulandari and Haryadi (2020) revealed that the GLS program at SMA N 1 Purworejo had an impact on increasing reading ability and increasing students' reading skills after participating in the GLS program. Then Agustin and Cahyono (2017) explained that the implementation of GLS in schools which was carried out in the morning or before learning had made students accustomed to reading books. To maintain students' reading ability, this is accompanied by the creation of student notebook models which aim to monitor students' book reading progress in class.

Referring to the research related above, this research is different and new, namely conducting a comparative study between two schools in the Tidore Islands from 2016 to 2019. It is hoped that this study will be able to provide constructive input to the government and schools implementing literacy programs. in the City of Tidore Islands to improve the same program in the future, so that this research can contribute to the study of the school literacy movement in the region and in Indonesia in general.

II. METHOD

The research uses a qualitative approach with a comparative model to analyze and compare phenomena or concepts related to the implementation of the school literacy movement. Basically, this method focuses on observing and understanding how certain variables are different or the same in a particular context. In comparative research methods, researchers can use a large number of different techniques to compare and analyze data, such as qualitative data collection (Creswell, 2017). Primary and secondary data originating from direct observation, interviews with informants are used as a basis for analyzing data to answer research questions.

Secondary data comes from analysis of documentation on the implementation of school literacy programs. Creswell (2017) explains that comparative studies are comparing two or more variables, subjects, locations, or groups. This means that comparative analysis uses data to test the relationships between variables to find associations or differences between them. The aim of comparative analysis is to find relationships between variables and identify differences between them. So data related to the implementation of the school literacy movement was taken using interviews, observation and documentation and then analyzed using comparative techniques. The analysis focuses on comparing the implementation of the stages of the school literacy movement, in order to be able to map the similarities or differences in its implementation in each school.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Implementation of GLS at SMA Negeri 1

The implementation of various stages in school literacy activities at SMA Negeri 1 has been carried out by teachers, school principals, and supported by students. The first step taken was that the principal together with the person in charge of literacy activities who was also an Indonesian language teacher told all teachers to start reading books in class. This effort is realized by reading books for fifteen minutes in the classroom. After that, continue with the lesson materials. In practice, teachers remind students in class to read general books properly and correctly, because they are given an assessment. This kind of activity started in 2016.

This effort provides euphoria among students. They seemed to be bringing various books to read together with their friends in class. In the process of improving reading ability, teachers also do not forget to check the type and content of books brought by students. This aims to ensure that the books they read are appropriate for their age and understanding. So that there are no misunderstandings in understanding the content of the reading. There are several books that teachers advise students not to read, such as comic books whose content is not in line with the school's efforts to form an intelligent young generation who practice polite language in everyday life.

However, there are still students who do not comply with bringing books to school. So the teachers implemented the strategy of borrowing books from the school library to them. Note that the books borrowed

must be returned on time because they are already on the list of book borrowers. If they don't return it, they will be given sanctions. However, there are still students who do not return the books they borrow from the library.

To optimize literacy activities at school, SMA Negeri 1 carried out organizational institutionalization. This aims to strengthen the governance and implementation of various school literacy activities in a structured and sustainable manner. So a school literacy team was formed around August 2016. This team is expected to form, compile and implement various school literacy programs. One of the first steps taken by the literacy team was to monitor the implementation of book reading in class and encourage teachers to actively participate in supporting this activity by creating reading journals for students.

1. Habituation Stage

SMA Negeri 1 has implemented the habit of reading a book for 15 minutes before learning activities begin, starting in 2016. The first hour subject teacher in each class supervises the implementation of this book reading, using the method of reading silently in class. This habit has been going on for more than one semester.

The teacher has an important role in controlling students when they read a book for 15 minutes. Teachers must guide students so that they can read books they bring from home or books borrowed from the library. Apart from that, teachers must also be an example for students by reading books in front of the class. After finishing reading, the teacher must ask students to record the name, book page, and date of reading the book in the reading monitor book or student journal in the GLS program.

Students at SMA Negeri 1 have tried to support the GLS program by building a library building and creating reading corners in each class. A reading corner competition was held in December 2017, but the problem faced was that the reading corner that had been created was only one year old. This is because students who are promoted to class and new students who enter the class will change and dismantle the existing reading corner. As a result, the reading corner often changes according to the wishes and tastes of the students in the class.

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SMA Negeri 1 has made various efforts to increase literacy among students. One way is to put up posters inviting people to read in several places, such as in school corridors and in school gardens. The school environment is also made clean so that students can read anywhere, especially in clean school gardens. Apart from that, healthy living habit posters are also installed in school canteens to promote healthy living at school. With these various efforts, it is hoped that students can improve literacy and live healthy lives at school.

Apart from that, the school also holds various literacy activities at school, such as book discussions, writing competitions, and so on. With these various activities, it is hoped that students can further improve their literacy and develop their thinking abilities.

Public participation is an important part of the GLS program at SMA Negeri 1. Therefore, SMA Negeri 1 opens a space for public participation by holding book exhibitions and book bazaars at school. Thus, it is hoped that public participation can help in developing GLS activities in schools.

2. Learning Stage

Implementation of the learning stages in the School Literacy Movement program at SMA Negeri 1 consists of efforts to promote literacy culture in schools. Teachers can do various things such as providing oral or written responses, creating a portfolio of reading response journals, providing non-academic assessments of students' oral and written responses, displaying journal of students' responses in the classroom or school corridor, appreciating students' achievements in literacy activities by giving awards, making reading campaign

posters, forming a school literacy team, holding academic activities that support school literacy culture such as trips to regional libraries or reading car visits traveling around, as well as holding activities to celebrate certain days related to literacy in schools.

3. Development Stage

The implementation of the habituation stage at SMA Negeri 1 consists of various activities such as explaining reading strategies and follow-up activities in oral and written form taught to students. Teachers use oral and written statements as academic assessments. Students are also taught to use literacy-rich physical, social, affective and academic environments to enrich knowledge in subjects. The results of academic bills, such as journals of students' responses from reading reading books and textbooks, are displayed in the classroom or in the school corridor. Awards are also given to students who succeed in literacy activities. Reading campaign posters were also put up to increase the understanding and enthusiasm of school residents to become lifelong learners. Performances of work (the result of critical thinking skills and the ability to communicate creatively verbally, in writing, visually or digitally) are also expected to be produced by students in celebration of certain days related to literacy. The school literacy team is tasked with planning, implementing and assessing school literacy programs. The school also coordinates with external parties to develop school literacy programs and increase the professionalism of school residents regarding literacy.

B. Implementation of GLS at SMA Negeri 3

The literacy program in schools is one of the government's efforts to improve students' reading ability. Through various literacy activities outlined by the implementing school, it is hoped that it will be able to encourage students' ability to understand and implement various reading materials that have been read while in the classroom. To carry out this activity, each school must do it in stages. Because this activity consists of habituation, development and learning stages. Specifically, SMA N 3 has carried out the habituation stage which starts with book reading activities in the classroom. This activity was implemented in 2017. Where students in grades 10-12 carry out the routine of reading books in the morning at the start of class.

In the process of reading books, students are not left alone in the classroom. The teacher who teaches the first lesson has the responsibility to evaluate the results of their reading. Each student is asked to make notes on their reading results and then submit them to the teacher. At this stage, not all students collect their reading results so the teacher needs to be firm. Because reading notes are an indicator to determine whether a student has finished reading a book in class or not. If they collect notes on the results of reading the book, it can be said that the student has finished reading the book.

To ensure this activity runs sustainably, the school, under the authority of the principal, holds joint meetings with all teachers. The results of the meeting decided that teachers were expected to oversee and monitor the process of reading books in class before teaching and learning activities were carried out. However, in reality, not all teachers have implemented this agreement. So reading books in class has not been effective.

In the course of literacy activities at SMA N 3, various suggestions emerged from teachers to include this activity as an assessment for students. This assessment aims to encourage students to actively read books in class. As a result, several teachers, such as Indonesian and mathematics teachers, have included it as one of the assessment points for students who read books and submit notes to the teacher. The implementation of literacy activities in schools reached its peak in 2017. The euphoria at school was felt by the presence of various activities and reading corners set up by students in each class. However, as time goes by, literacy activities have decreased in 2018-2019. This is because there is no ongoing coordination between schools and the local Education Office in optimizing and evaluating literacy programs in schools.

1. Habituation Stage

SMA Negeri 3 has implemented the GLS program through book reading activities for 15 minutes before studying, has a library equipped with a collection of non-study books, as well as the involvement of teachers in book reading activities. However, the formation of reading corners in classrooms has not been

carried out until August 2019. Therefore, the school will start socializing the creation of reading corners with the assistance of the Tidore Islands City Regional Library starting September-October. Apart from that, the school library also does not have a comfortable atmosphere due to the lack of chairs. Therefore, the school had to borrow library chairs to cover the shortage of seats in class. The arrangement of the non-study book collection in the library has also not been done properly because there are no non-study book names on the shelves.

Apart from that, SMA Negeri 3 also held a reading corner competition between classes within the school as part of the GLS program. To create a reading culture at school, the school also recommends reading books in class. This aims to enable students to develop their reading skills. Teachers also play a big role in inviting students to read the books available at school.

The library guard at SMA Negeri 3 Hadija M Taher explained that the library was being cleaned and reorganized. Therefore, non-learning books which are included in the fiction and non-fiction categories have not been arranged properly. However, in the future library users will be able to see all the available books in an easier way because each bookshelf will be labeled.

SMA Negeri 3 has stated its commitment to implementing the GLS program. However, there has been no follow-up action to support literacy activities in schools. For this reason, it is hoped that there will be other programs besides meetings with teachers to carry out 15 minute book reading activities, such as forming a school literacy team.

SMA Negeri 3 has not been able to carry out several familiarization activities such as recording students' daily journals, placing posters for reading in classrooms or school corridors, providing a comfortable reading room, displaying written texts in each class, and inviting the wider community to school literacy activities.

Students' collective journals containing the reading topics they have done during the 15 minute book reading activity have been collected in the student affairs section. However, the preparation of the journal had not been carried out properly because the collective journal had been left alone without being placed in a cupboard or room.

SMA Negeri 3 has taken advantage of the shady atmosphere due to the large trees that grow around the school to provide coolness for the children. However, unfortunately schools have not taken further steps by providing literacy-themed posters and text-rich materials in classrooms. This will certainly help increase children's interest in literacy activities outside the classroom.

As a follow-up to the appeal given to grade 3 students who want to graduate, the school invites them to contribute by donating books to the library. This activity has been carried out for a long time and has received a positive response from students. However, there has been no effort to involve parents, alumni and other elements of society. The school is making efforts to invite students, parents, alumni and community members to contribute to building a library. This activity has been going on for a long time and received a positive response from the students. However, broad community participation is still insufficient to support this program.

2. Development Stage

Various activities that are indicators in the development stages of the school literacy program at SMA Negeri 3 have not been implemented. This is because SMA N 3 has not received socialization regarding the implementation of the program as a whole from the familiarization, development and learning stages. Literacy activities that have not been implemented at SMA N 3 are that students' oral and written responses have not been measured using non-academic assessments, student response journals have not been displayed in the classroom or school corridors, students' achievements have not been appreciated by giving awards, there are no campaign posters. reading, there is no School Literacy Team, there are no academic activities that support school literacy culture, such as trips to regional libraries or mobile reading car visits, and there are no activities to celebrate certain days related to literacy at school.

3. Learning Stage

Literacy activities in schools have several stages, one of which is the learning stage as the peak. Not all schools that implement literacy programs are able to reach the learning stage. Because it is influenced by various factors. This is what happened at SMA N 3. Several factors such as a school literacy team that has not been formed, literacy program guidelines that have not been thoroughly explained to teachers and teaching staff at the school and the development of learning strategies for students using various approaches has not been carried out.

The various factors above directly influence the quality and quantity of implementing the stages of literacy activities in schools. Students have not been directed to use an inclusive environment for school literacy activities. Where several literacy facilities and infrastructure in schools are not yet adequate, for example notebooks, positive campaign pictures about literacy, presentations of student work, and the initiation of the institutionalization of literacy teams in schools.

C. Comparison of the Implementation of School Literacy Movements

Literacy activities carried out in each school can be described as having entered several stages. A comparison of the two schools when viewed from the aspect of implementing the stages of the school literacy program, means that SMA Negeri 3 is still at the initial level of the literacy program. In this school, it was found that teachers together with students had carried out the practice of reading books at school. The time span for students to read books is around 15 minutes in the classroom before the start of learning.

It can be said that SMA Negeri 3 is implementing the stages of the school literacy program only up to the habituation stage. This is indicated by the provision of reading materials in the school library consisting of textbooks and general books for students. Meanwhile, the follow-up to the implementation of the development and learning stages has not been carried out by the school management. This is because they are hampered by the guidelines for implementing the stages of literacy activities in schools. So the implementation of the three stages of the school literacy program has not proceeded according to the objectives of the program.

Meanwhile, SMA Negeri 1 has made various efforts to increase literacy among students through the habituation, learning and development stages. So this school on Tidore Island has been running a school literacy program since 2016, while at SMA Negeri 3 it only started running literacy activities in 2017. The GLS program at SMA Negeri 1 includes reading books for 15 minutes in class, building a library building, creating a reading corner, installing posters inviting reading, holding various literacy activities, opening space for public participation, and teaching reading strategies. A School Literacy Team was also formed to monitor the implementation of the GLS program. With these various efforts, students can be encouraged to strengthen literacy and live healthy lives at school.

Based on the comparative study of the implementation of GLS activities in SMA N 1 and SMA N 3 above, it is necessary to make several efforts to strengthen the GLS program by referring to relevant research results. Where the implementation of GLS in two schools still found weaknesses such as the absence of training for teachers, collaboration between schools and parties outside the school not being optimized, and innovation and creativity of teachers and students in implementing GLS. So some of the research below can be used as a basis for strengthening the implementation of GLS in the future.

Based on Suprahatini's (2018) research results, several activities were found that could support school literacy activities. Such as Reading Group, which is a program packaged in a class activity to hone and measure students' abilities in knowing English and German. Apart from that, there are also Hello Brow activities...? to build students' personal branding in telling stories in front of the entire school community. Then, there is the Library Corner which aims to fulfill the need for reading books in the classroom library. However, the book collection there does not meet the students' wishes. Finally, there is Cangkrukan, which is an activity adapted from Surabaya people's habits of discussing and discussing problems in various places such as coffee shops, patrol posts, malls, etc. At school, Cangkrukan is done in the school cafe during break times or after school. Meanwhile, on the mosque terrace, Cangkrukan is only done on Fridays. After Friday prayers, school residents

usually sit in groups on the mosque terrace while talking and discussing the lessons that have been carried out throughout the week.

Castelli, Barcelona, and Bryant's (2015) study related to the literacy movement regarding physical and spiritual education for students in the United States shows that government efforts to implement literacy education for students in schools must be supported by various factors such as a whole school approach, effective pedagogical methods, and differently, the use of technology in measuring student literacy progress, a supportive school climate, and the synergy of all local to national elements. Then Abbott, et al (2020) found in Rwanda that the government's efforts to implement literacy education will be in vain if it is not supported by tutor/teacher training and improving infrastructure and learning resources. Not only that, the poor quality of implementing literacy activities in schools is a major obstacle to student learning. These two studies provide an illustration that implementing literacy programs in schools must receive support and be followed by various strengthening activities for all stakeholders implementing the program.

Meanwhile, Kamil, Utaya, and Utomo (2020) in their research in Banda Aceh City regarding literacy activities in high schools regarding disasters using geography subjects. Where is the role of teachers in using geographical perspective-based teaching materials to support disaster risk reduction learning. So that students have good disaster response skills and find solutions to natural damage and reduce its negative effects. This research provides the view that to develop literacy education in schools, they must be able to creatively use existing potential to actualize literacy themes in the learning process, so that students are able to capture the messages and content presented.

Meanwhile, a study from O'Neil, et al (2020) revealed that education in schools must open up space for collaboration between the public and the private sector. Especially activities that require implementation in the field. As in the Chesapeake Program which deals with environmental literacy and ecology in high schools in the United States. Where the teacher designs a question-and-answer-based field investigation for students to use when going into the field to observe the environment and ecology in the Chesapeake. So that students have good disaster response skills and find solutions to natural damage and reduce its negative effects. This study provides an illustration that implementing literacy programs in schools must open up space for collaboration with external parties. As with the implementation of GLS above, it has not optimally involved various external parties to support literacy activities in schools.

IV. CONCLUSION

School literacy activities on Tidore Island which were implemented at the high school (SMA) level were carried out in 2016. In a study conducted at SMA Negeri 1 and SMA Negeri 3, it was found that SMA 1 had implemented all stages of the school literacy program, while SMA 3 had only at the habituation stage. This shows that the implementation of GSL in SMA 1 is more optimal than in SMA 3. Therefore, the results of this research show that SMA 1 is more optimal than SMA 3 in implementing the stages of the literacy program at school. SMA 1 has successfully implemented all stages of the GSL program, while SMA 3 has only reached the familiarization stage. This shows that SMA 1 has been more successful in implementing various indicators of school literacy cultivation.

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